

STYLISTICS IN THE SYSTEM OF LINGUISTIC INVESTIGATIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11399109>

Annotation. The article provides that the usage of Stylistics and its devices in the sphere of Linguistics. It explains the aspects of Stylistics in Linguistic investigation and theory of formation in linguistic contexts.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada Stilistika va uning ifoda vositalarini Lingvistikada qo'llanilishini izohlaydi hamda Stilistikani lingvistik nazariyalarida va matnlarida qo'llanilishini tushuntirib beradi.

Key words: linguistics, devices, descriptive, semantic, category

Introduction

Stylistics is a domain where meaning assumes paramount importance.. This is so because the term 'meaning' is applied not only to words, word-combinations, sentences but also to the manner of expression into which the matter is cast. "The linguistic term meaning has been "defined in so many ways that there appears an urgent need to clarify it; particularly in view of the fact that in so many lexical, grammatical and phonetic SDs this category is treated differently. It has already been mentioned that a stylistic device is mainly realized when a twofold application of meaning is apparent. At some period in the development of a certain trend in linguistic theory in America, viz. descriptive linguistics, meaning was excluded from observations in language science; it was considered an extra-linguistic category.

The tendency was so strong that R. Jakobson proposed the term "semantic invariant" as a substitute for "meaning". "If, however, you dislike the word meaning because it is too ambiguous," writes R. Jakobson, "then let us simply deal with semantic invariants, no less important for linguistic analysis than the phonemic invariants." But this tendency has been ruled out by later research in language data. One of the prominent American scientists, Wallace L. Chafe, is right when he states that "...the data of meaning are both accessible to linguistic explanation and crucial to the investigation of language structure — in certain ways more crucial than the data of sound to which linguistic studies have given such unbalanced attention." The problem of meaning in general linguistics deals mainly with such aspects of the term as the interrelation between meaning and concept, meaning and sign, meaning and referent. The general tendency is to regard meaning as something stable at a given period of time. This is reasonable, otherwise no dictionary would be able to cope with the problem of defining the

meaning of words. Moreover, no communication would be possible. In stylistics meaning is also viewed as a category which is able to acquire meaning sponsored on the words by the context. That is why such “meanings are called contextual meanings. This category also takes under observation meanings which have fallen out of use. In stylistics it is important to discriminate shades or nuances of meaning, to atomize the meaning, the component parts of which are now called the semes i.e. the smallest units of which meaning of a Word consists. “A proper concern for meanings,” writes W. Chafe, “should lead to a situation where, in the training of linguists, practice in the discrimination of concepts will be given at least as much time in the curriculum as practice in the discrimination of sounds.” It will be shown later, in the analysis of SDs, how important it is to discriminate between the meanings of a given word or construction in order to adequately comprehend the idea and purport of a passage and of a complete work.

It is now common knowledge that lexical meaning Differs from grammatical meaning in more than one way. Lexical cat meaning refers the mind to some concrete concept, phenomenon, or thing of objective reality, whether real or imaginary. Lexical meaning is thus a means by which a word-form is made to express a definite concept. Grammatical meaning refers our mind to relations between words or to some forms of-words or constructions bearing upon their structural functions in the language as a system. Grammatical meaning can thus be adequately called “structural meaning”.

There are no words which are deprived of grammatical meaning inasmuch as all words belong to some system and consequently have their place in the system, and also inasmuch as they always function in speech displaying their functional properties. It is the same with sentences. Every sentence has its own independent structural meaning. This structural meaning may in some cases be influenced or affected by the lexical meanings of the components or by intonation. In the sentence 'I shall never go to that place again¹, we have a number of words with lexical meanings (never, go, place, again) and words with only grammatical meaning (shall, that) and also the meaning of the whole sentence, which is defined as a structure in statement form. But each of the meanings, being closely interwoven and interdependent, can none the less be regarded as relatively autonomous and therefore be analyzed separately. It is significant that words acquire different status when analyzed in isolation or in the sentence. This double aspect causes in the long run the growth of the

semantic structure of a word, especially when the two aspects frequently interweave.

Words can be classed according to different principles: morphological (“(parts of speech), semantic (synonyms, antonyms, thematic), stylistic, and other types of classification. In each of these classifications lexical or/and grammatical meanings assume different manifestations. In a morphological classification words are grouped according to their grammatical meanings; in a semantic classification, according to their logical (referential) meanings, in a stylistic classification, according to their stylistic meaning. Lexical meanings are closely related to concepts. They are sometimes identified with concepts. But concept is a purely logical category, whereas meaning is a linguistic one. In linguistics it is necessary to view meaning as the representation of a concept through one of its properties. Concept, as is known, is versatile; it is characterized by a number of properties. Meaning takes one of these properties and makes it represent the concept as a whole. Therefore meaning in reference to concept becomes, as it were, a kind of metonymy. This statement is significant in as much as it will further explain the stylistic function of certain meanings. One and the same concept can be represented in a number of linguistic manifestations (meanings) but, paradox though it may sound, each manifestation causes a slight (and sometimes considerable) modification of the concept, in other words, discloses latent or unknown properties of the concept. “The variability of meanings,” writes R. Jakobson, “their manifold and far reaching figurative shifts, and an incalculable aptitude for multiple paraphrases are just those properties of natural language which induce its creativity and endow not only poetic but even scientific activities with a continuously inventive sweep. Here the indefiniteness and creative power appear to be wholly interrelated.” The inner property of language, which may be defined as self-generating, is apparent in meaning. It follows then that the creativity of linguistics in Relation to Other Sciences.— In: “Selected-Works”. language so often referred to in this work, lies in this particular category of language science — meaning.[Rein,1989]

The variability of “meanings caused by the multifarious practical application of the basic (fundamental) meaning when .used in speech has led to the birth of a notion known as polysemantic. This is a linguistic category which contains a great degree of ambiguity. On the one hand, we perceive meaning as a representation of a definite concept by means of a word. On the other hand, we state that the same concept may be expressed by different meanings all belonging to the same word [Рыбочкина,2012;190-195].

Still more confusing is the well-recognized fact that different concepts may be expressed by one and the same word. But such is the very nature of language, where contradiction, ambiguity and uncertainty run parallel with rigidity, strictness and conformity to standard requirements of grammatical acceptability. S. D. Katznelson remarks in this connection that “a lexical meaning may... conflict with the basic functional meaning of its class remaining, however, within its own class.”

The ability of a word to be polysemantic, i.e. to comprise several lexical meanings, becomes a crucial issue for stylistic studies. It must be clearly understood that the multitude of meanings that a word may have is not limited by dictionaries where this multitude has already been recognized and fixed. Some meanings, which for the time being have not as yet been recognized as legitimate members of the semantic structure of the given word, may, in the course of time, through frequent use become such and subsequently become fixed in dictionaries. Convincing proof of this are the so-called addenda to new editions of dictionaries where new meanings are presented as already recognized facts of language. A stylistic approach to the issue in question takes into consideration the fact that every word, no matter how rich in meanings it may be, leaves the door open for new shades and nuances and even for independent meanings. True, such meanings are not always easily accepted as normal. Moreover, many of them are rejected both by scholars and the people and therefore are not recognized as facts of language. Such meanings become obscure in the family of lexical meanings of a word; they can only be traced back to the original use. However, some of these meanings are occasionally re-established in the vocabulary at a later time. Lexical meaning, be it repeated, is a conventional category. Very frequently it does not reflect the properties of the thing or the phenomenon it refers to. However, some meanings are said to be motivated, i.e. they point to some quality or feature of the object.

Conclusion

Teaching Stylistics is based on a technical terminology with which students can describe stylistic choices. Much of this technical terminology is in practice borrowed from traditional grammar or a linguistic theory.

References:

1. Craig H. Stylistics or Cognitive Stylistics? 2006.102
2. Crystal D., Davy, D. Investigating English Style. Harlow: Addison Wesley Longman, 1969. 264 p.

3. Dahlén, M., & Rosengren, S. // Brands affect slogans affect brands? Competitive interference, brand equity and the brand-slogan link. *Journal of Brand Management*; 12(3). 2005.
4. Dean D. Brand endorsement, popularity, and event sponsorship as advertising cues affecting consumer pre-purchase attitudes. *Journal of Advertising*, 1-12. 1999.

